

USE OF MODERN TECHNOLOGIES IN IMPROVING THE METHODOLOGY FOR DEVELOPING STUDENTS' PROFESSIONAL COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCIES BASED ON ECONOMIC TERMS IN TEACHING ENGLISH TO STUDENTS STUDYING FORESTRY

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Abstract. *This research explores the use of modern technologies in enhancing the methodology for developing professional communicative competencies in students studying forestry. By focusing on economic terms, the study aims to identify effective teaching strategies that leverage technological tools to improve English language instruction. The findings will provide insights into how modern educational technologies can facilitate better learning outcomes for students, equipping them with the necessary skills to communicate professionally in the field of forestry.*

Keywords: *modern technologies, methodology, professional communicative competencies, economic terms, teaching English, forestry, students, learning process, teaching methods, quick results.*

Introduction

English is widely spoken around the world and has become a primary means of global communication. In today's modern world, the integration of technology significantly enhances the effectiveness and productivity of the English teaching process. Students now have access to various digital tools that enrich traditional teaching methods.

Educational technologies are particularly important for effectively teaching English to students studying forestry. The use of modern technologies such as speakers, televisions, radios, electronic dictionaries, and electronic boards provides students with an engaging and interactive learning experience. These tools enable educators to present interesting educational videos, cartoons, audio materials, and interactive content, helping to capture students' attention and facilitate better comprehension of the subject matter.

The purpose of this study is to examine the impact of modern technologies on teaching English. Data for the research was collected using a mixed-method approach, which included administering questionnaires to students and conducting classroom observations. It is important to note that this type of research is inevitably limited by various constraints, particularly the sample size of the students, which was restricted to those studying forestry. These limitations are crucial in ensuring the reliability and validity of the research findings.

The results of this study are expected to provide valuable insights into the effectiveness of modern technologies in teaching English and improving the learning process.

General information about literary sources; literary commentary. For many years, methods of teaching English have been characterized by a traditional one-sided approach known as test-oriented teaching. This method is viewed as a testing-focused approach, which can impose certain limitations on students' language acquisition processes. In this method, words,

phrases, and collocations are learned through memorization, creating a heavy burden during the learning process (Vang & Dostal, 2017, pp. 3814-3820).

The development of English language education is evolving to meet modern requirements, necessitating updates to curricula and methodologies. Currently, English classes pay special attention to various aspects of language arts, including composition, literature, decoding, reading comprehension, spelling, vocabulary, grammar, usage, punctuation, capitalization, brainstorming, planning, reasoning, note-taking, utilizing information, learning skills, rhetoric, handwriting, drama, and more (Bruce & Levin, 2001). This multifaceted approach helps cultivate well-rounded students and further enhances their English language skills.

Recent research has shown that integrating modern technologies into the process of teaching English can significantly improve the quality of education. For example, interactive teaching tools, online platforms, and multimedia materials encourage students to actively participate and make the learning process more engaging (Vang, Teng, and Chen, 2015, pp. 100-104). This not only makes the knowledge acquisition process more effective and convenient but also fosters students' self-learning and problem-solving skills.

The integration of modern technologies serves not only to enhance knowledge acquisition but also to develop students' self-awareness and independent thinking as language users in the process of learning English. Educators can organize their classes more effectively by utilizing contemporary educational methodologies and create the best possible learning environment for students.

Overall, the role of modern technologies in teaching English not only presents new opportunities against traditional approaches but also helps students develop the communicative competencies necessary for success in a global environment.

Methodology.

A qualitative research method was employed to assess the impact and significance of modern technologies on the process of learning English among students. The study involved a total of 15 students who initially participated in traditional lessons. In these lessons, no modern teaching aids, such as videos, electronic boards, or speakers, were utilized. Students were required to memorize vocabulary through regular repetition, with the teacher explaining the topics directly on the board. Handouts were provided for exercises throughout the lesson, creating an environment more aligned with traditional teaching methods.

In the second phase of the lessons, modern technologies, such as interactive presentations and multimedia materials, were effectively integrated into the teaching process. In this lesson, speakers were used to provide students with the opportunity to listen to the speech of native speakers, enhancing their listening skills and pronunciation. This contrast between the two teaching approaches allowed for a direct comparison of the effectiveness of traditional methods versus those that incorporate modern technologies.

To further enhance the reliability of the research findings, a questionnaire was distributed to a larger sample of 50 students. This survey aimed to delve deeper into the relevance of modern technologies in their learning experience and to gain a better understanding of how these tools impact their education. The complete list of questions included in the questionnaire is as follows:

1. How do you memorize new words?
2. Do you find it helpful to learn new topics through PowerPoint presentations?
3. Do you find topics presented on the blackboard interesting?

4. What do you think about watching animated movies related to the subject?
5. What are convenient ways for you to improve pronunciation?
6. Do you enjoy listening to podcasts?
7. Do educational video games help you learn English effectively?
8. How do you feel about receiving homework assignments from teachers?
9. How do you usually find the translation of new words?
10. How do you learn the pronunciation of new words?

These questions are designed to elucidate the relationship between students and modern technologies. The insights gathered from the questionnaire are crucial for enhancing the precision of the research, as they not only capture students' perceptions regarding modern technologies but also investigate the most effective methods for learning English and how they find it convenient to learn.

By analyzing the responses to the questionnaire alongside the observations made during the lessons, this study aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of how modern technologies can be leveraged to improve the teaching and learning of English. The findings are expected to contribute valuable insights into best practices for integrating technology into language education, ultimately benefiting both educators and students.

Overall, this research aims to reveal the importance of modern technologies in the educational process and illuminate the outcomes of efforts made to enhance students' language learning experiences. Furthermore, it may assist educators in developing convenient and effective teaching methods for students.

Results. In today's world, where the internet controls everything, it is difficult to deny the importance of technology in teaching English. Various forms of technology and media, including websites, mobile applications, podcasts, electronic workbooks, e-learning platforms, and educational videos, play a crucial role in making the learning process more effective and engaging. One of the biggest challenges in teaching a second language is motivating students to effectively learn English. The success of this process depends on many factors, and educators need to invest a significant amount of time and effort in identifying the most fulfilling, applicable, and effective teaching strategies for their students.

Listening Skills. In traditional classes, when modern technological resources are not utilized, students may be deprived of the opportunity to hear the pronunciation and speaking style of native speakers. This can lead to difficulties in memorizing new vocabulary during lessons, negatively affecting their interest and engagement in the class. Although the teacher teaches the pronunciation of new words, and students attempt to learn these words through repetition and interactive games, none of these methods can replace the importance of listening to audio recordings of native speakers. Such listening experiences are vital for developing pronunciation and comprehension skills in English. Consequently, students feel more engaged, attentive, and motivated, making the educational process significantly more effective.

Grammar Understanding. When introducing new grammar topics through traditional methods, students often show little reluctance or disinterest in the verb-related activities. They perform various exercises to gain a better understanding of the topic. However, when the same grammar topic is presented using modern technologies, the students' comprehension and the results from subsequent question-and-answer sessions improve significantly. The use of modern technologies, particularly electronic whiteboards, allows for the introduction of colorful clusters and visually appealing diagrams that pique students' interest and encourage participation. This

engaging approach not only enhances their understanding but also increases their motivation to actively participate in discussions.

Conclusion. The results of this research clearly demonstrate the transformative potential of modern technologies in teaching English. By bridging the gap between traditional methods and modern technological tools, educators can significantly enhance their students' learning experiences. Listening to native speakers and employing interactive and visual aids not only improve comprehension and pronunciation but also create a more engaging and motivating learning environment. Therefore, embracing technology in teaching English is not merely an option but a necessity in today's digital age, ensuring that the language learning process is both effective and dynamic.

These research findings can guide educators in learning how to effectively integrate modern technologies into English language instruction, potentially improving student comprehension and retention. Overall, the use of modern technologies not only enriches the educational process but also creates more convenient and effective learning opportunities for students.

Discussion. Most young students have extensive access to information through the Internet, providing teachers with a wide array of tools to encourage and enhance various language skills. In Turkey, a quasi-experimental study was conducted by Isik and Yilmaz (2011) to evaluate the effectiveness of computer-assisted listening instruction on the listening comprehension of 21 students. The results revealed that the experimental group, which received multimedia-aided instruction, scored significantly higher than the control group, which received traditional language instruction. These findings highlight the essential role that modern technologies can play in activating students' engagement in the learning process, improving their listening skills, and enhancing the overall educational experience.

Moreover, Vacca (2008) emphasizes that when students are provided with the necessary materials, guidance, and support, they become more responsible for their own learning. This empowerment not only increases their motivation but also leads to greater academic success. The integration of technology in education does not merely serve as a tool for instructors; it actively fosters a more interactive and engaging learning environment among students. By leveraging technology, educators can cater to diverse learning styles, making lessons more accessible and enjoyable for all students.

Conclusion. The use of new technology allows students to be much more creative and participative in the classroom. Students can gather knowledge outside of the classroom by engaging with various course content. When they arrive in class, they share this knowledge with their peers and the teacher, effectively demonstrating what they have learned and reinforcing it in a coordinated manner. Educational technology equips students to be better prepared for class, and it provides teachers with appealing resources that make their lessons more interactive and social. In such environments, all students have the opportunity to participate, regardless of their proficiency levels.

Ultimately, the incorporation of modern technologies into language instruction not only enriches the educational process but also creates a more effective and dynamic learning atmosphere. By embracing these advancements, educators can significantly enhance student comprehension, engagement, and retention of the English language, ensuring that the learning experience is both impactful and meaningful.

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